

RECENT ADVANCES IN MAMMOGRAPHY

Sapna Sahu^{1*}, Mandeep Kumar¹, Ijen Bhattacharya²

- 1- Radiology & Imaging Technology, Government Institute of Medical Sciences (GIMS), Greater Noida (U.P.)-India
- 2- Professor, Department of Biochemistry Government Institute of Medical Sciences (GIMS), Greater Noida (U.P.)-India

* Corresponding Author:
Prof. Ijen Bhattacharya
Department of Biochemistry
GIMS, Greater Noida (U.P.)-India

ABSTRACT:-

Breast tomosynthesis is made possible by digital mammography systems. Particularly in women with radiographically dense breasts, tomosynthesis may enhance early breast cancer detection and increase the specificity of mammography by improving lesion margin visibility.

Several digital technologies that are being developed to solve the weaknesses of conventional mammography (film screen and/or digital mammography [DM]) are discussed in this article. With a secondary discussion of Contrast-Enhanced Digital Mammography, the focus is on digital breast tomosynthesis. The US Food and Drug Administration has not yet authorised any of the aforementioned technologies for clinical use; they are all currently in the investigational stage in the US. Regulatory approval and scientific research will decide whether these technologies are utilised in medical settings.

Keywords- Breast Cancer, Breast imaging, Digital breast tomosynthesis, Tumors, Screening mammography, Diagnostic imaging

INTRODUCTION-

Mammography is a specialised form of breast radiography that creates images of the breast using x-rays. Screening mammography is used to detect breast cancer early before symptoms appear, and diagnostic mammography, also known as clinical mammography, is used to diagnose patients who have symptoms like a palpable lump.

Both benign diseases and malignant tumours (cancers) are highly prevalent in the breast. The so-called clinical breast examination consists of clinical history (disorders in the family, prior breast diseases/surgery, hormone therapy, personal well-being and complaints), inspection (external viewing), and palpation. Imaging procedures, particularly mammography, are crucial in the diagnosis and detection of breast cancer and other breast diseases [1].

Around the world, breast cancer remains to be the leading cause of death for women. Among women in developed countries is the most prevalent cancer, and the second or third most prevalent type of cancer in developing nations' female population. Digital mammography has replaced conventional mammography in the United States. Both digital and conventional mammography use x-rays to create an image of the breast; however, digital mammography stores an electronic image of the breast as a computer file, while conventional mammography stores the image directly on film. Compared to information recorded on film, this digital data is easier to enhance, magnify, or manipulate for additional analysis. Additionally, digital images can be shared electronically, which facilitates virtual (remote) consultations between breast surgeons and radiologists.

Conventional film-screen mammography has gradually been replaced by digital mammography, which is now the gold standard when combined with soft copy reading in screening and diagnostic settings. In terms of breast cancer detectability, large international multi-center trials were able to show at least equivalency and, in some cases, superiority of digital over conventional mammography, particularly in pre/perimenopausal women, women under 50, and women with dense breasts in general. With its increased specificity, CAD may be especially helpful to the advanced reader. Early detection of breast cancer and a decrease in mortality among breast cancer patients are two important benefits of computer-aided detection or diagnosis (CAD) systems [2]. With computer-aided detection (CAD) systems, radiologists can detect mammogram lesions that may be indications of breast cancer. They appear only as a second reader; the radiologist has the last indicate.[3] Among the modalities are magnetic resonance imaging, digital mammography, digital breast tomosynthesis, breast ultrasonography, and clinical breast examination [4]

Furthermore, advanced processing options like digital tomosynthesis and contrast-enhanced mammography are available with digital mammography. The integration of various imaging systems (hybrid systems) will be the way of the future for breast imaging [5].

SCREENING AND DIAGNOSTIC MAMMOGRAPHY

The most crucial imaging technique for identifying and diagnosing breast cancer is mammography. The overall goal is to make it possible to treat breast cancer early, increase survival rates, and lessen the need for extreme procedures like mastectomy [6] especially in the current era of advanced therapies [7,8]. It can be carried out in a diagnostic or screening context. Given a number of pertinent benefits for both the women receiving the mammogram and the general public, such as reduced x-ray dose, improved image quality, post-processing choices, digital archiving, image transmission, and no chemical pollution, full-field digital mammography (not phosphor-plate computer radiography) should be preferred over film-screen mammography in both circumstances whenever acceptable.

SAFETY MEASURES

A less invasive mammogram can be performed most effectively between days 7 and 12 following the start of the woman's most recent menstrual cycle. There is no specific scheduling needed after menopause, which suggests that scheduling is permissible for most mammograms conducted as part of population-based screening programs. Ultrasound is the advised first course of treatment if the woman is pregnant.

ADVANCES IN MAMMOGRAPHY TECHNOLOGY

Screen film mammography (SFM) is a good evaluation, but it is not highly precise or entirely sensitive. It is significantly limited in its ability to identify subtle soft tissue lesions indicating of breast cancer, particularly in the dense breast tissue present. Since many carcinomas go undetected, efforts are being made to enhance mammography's ability to identify cancers early. Over the past 25 years, there have been significant developments in screen/film recording systems and mammography X-ray equipment [9]. Prior to the mid-1980s, a lot of X-ray machines weren't specifically designed for mammography. Tungsten target tubes, which were initially intended for use in other medical imaging procedures like chest radiography, were

present in these units. A lot of these units used homemade compression equipment that was unable to guarantee sufficient breast compression. Nowadays, specialised mammography X-ray equipment is used for mammograms [9]. These devices include smaller focal spots, specially made X-ray tubes, and among other things, breast compression devices have been greatly enhanced. The various tungsten, molybdenum, and rhodium targets in modern X-ray tubes are selected by a microprocessor to provide the best tissue penetration. Special films, intensifying screens, and cassettes are made specifically for mammography. The main weak point causing issues with image quality and artefacts has been film processing. However, over time, this has also greatly improved. Compared to 25 years ago, mammograms can now be obtained with better image quality and at a much lower radiation dose. The US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) authorised the mammography system for clinical use. The recent transforming stages of mammography technology advancements are listed in Table 1[12]

Table 1. The recent transforming stages of mammography technology advancements

YEAR	DEVELOPMENT	ORGANISATION
Before 1969	Conventional tungsten target X-ray tubes with direct exposure industrial type film	
1969	Dedicated mammographic unit with molybdenum target tube and compression Compagnie	Compagnie Generale Radiologie device Senographe
1971	Xeromammography	Xerox
1972	Screen-film system	Du Pont Lo-dose system
1976	Rare earth screen-film system and special cassette	Kodak Min-R system
1977	Magnification with microfocal spot	Radiological Sciences Inc.
1978	Grid	Philips
1987	American College of Radiology Mammography Accreditation Program	American College of Radiology
1992	American College of Radiology Mammography Quality Control Manual introduced	American College of Radiology

1994	Mammography Quality Standards Act (MQSA) implementation	Food and Drug Administration
2000	First digital mammography approved by the USA Food and Drug Administration for clinical use	General Electric Senographe 2000D

ADVANCED IMAGING TECHNIQUES-

Digital breast tomosynthesis- A three-dimensional variation of digital mammography (DM), digital breast tomosynthesis (DBT, also known as 3D-mammography) lessens the impact of tissue superimposition and could enhance mammogram interpretation [7].

Digital breast tomosynthesis, has quickly become a significant new imaging technique that improves the detection of breast cancer by minimising the masking effect of overlapping fibroglandular tissue. Multiple low-dose x-ray exposures are obtained while the x-ray tube moves across a narrow arc above the breast to create tomosynthesis images. Various manufacturers have different specifications for the tube's motion, the arc's length, and the time required to produce a full set of projection images that are reconstructed into thin image slices separated by 0.5 to 1.0 mm. GE Healthcare showed that DBT could significantly increase lesion visibility (Fig. 1) and lower screening recall rates [8].

Fig. 1A —57-year-old woman with breast cancer. Comparison of standard 2D versus digital breast tomosynthesis (DBT).

A, Standard 2D digital mammogram shows very dense breast.

TOMOSYNTHESIS-GUIDED PROCEDURES

No specialised equipment is required to perform tomosynthesis-guided needle localisation. The only necessary equipment is the DBT unit and standard open-window compression paddles. It is easy to perform preoperative wire or seed localisation of lesions that are only visible on DBT. However, the gold standard for care is an initial image-guided core needle biopsy (CNB) and histologic sampling of suspicious breast lesions, which is typically preferred by breast surgeons and patients alike. While preoperative diagnosis of malignant lesions allows for better surgical planning and may reduce the number of open surgical procedures required for appropriate patient management, the diagnosis of benign lesions may preclude surgery (unless the initial diagnosis is a high-risk lesion or associated with atypia) [10].

CONTRAST-ENHANCED MAMMOGRAPHY (CEM)-

Contrast-enhanced mammography (CEM) was commercially introduced in 2011 and is an emerging breast imaging tool. For conducting Contrast Enhanced Digital Mammography examinations, two methods have been developed: the dual energy technique, which acquires a pair of low and high-energy images only after contrast medium injection, and the temporal subtraction technique, which acquires high-energy images both before and after contrast medium injection [11].

Contrast-enhanced mammography (CEM) has become a viable alternative for contrast-enhanced breast MRI, and it has the potential to lower examination costs while expanding access to vascular imaging. Tumour neovascularity is better visualised in CEM by using intravenous iodinated contrast materials. Prior to image acquisition, an intravenous injection of a low-osmolarity iodine-based contrast agent is administered. Depending on the facility, either a technologist or a nurse inserts the intravenous line. The contrast material's iodine concentration can range from 300 to 370 mg/mL. A saline flush is performed after administering a total volume of 1.5 mL/kg of body weight (up to 150 mL), ideally with an injector (injection rate, 2-3 mL/sec). After the injection of contrast material, image acquisition starts two to three minutes later. Each breast is viewed from a standard craniocaudal and mediolateral oblique views (**Figure 2**). If more views (such as rolled or compression views) are required, there is frequently ample time because contrast material may remain in tissue for up to 10 minutes.

Dual-energy digital mammography is used for imaging after injection. This helps produce a low-energy image and a recombined or iodine image that show enhancing breast lesions. It has been shown that CEM can increase accuracy when compared to digital mammography and US in women who have abnormal screening mammogram results or breast cancer symptoms. It has also been shown to be comparable to breast MRI in terms of preoperative staging of patients with breast cancer and response monitoring following neoadjuvant chemotherapy. Trials determining CEM in the screening of women with an elevated risk of breast cancer have produced initial positive findings. Although CEM is a promising tool, there is a slight chance of negative reactions to contrast materials and a small rise in radiation dose [9]. In general, malignant breast tumours demonstrate a quicker and more intense uptake of contrast than either benign or normal breast parenchyma [12].

Figure 2: Diagram of imaging protocol for contrast-enhanced mammography. Two minutes before image acquisition, iodine-based contrast material is injected. Next, at minimum, both breasts are imaged in craniocaudal and mediolateral oblique views. In each step, compression is applied (red arrow), followed by rapid acquisition of low- and high-energy images. These images are processed to generate low-energy and recombined images. After each exposure, compression is released (green arrow). Images are considered to be of diagnostic value if they are acquired within 10 minutes after contrast material administration. mins. = minutes.

THE BREAST IMAGING REPORTING AND DATA SYSTEM (BI-RADS)-

The Breast Imaging Reporting and Data System (BI-RADS) is a standardized system of reporting breast pathology encountered on mammography, ultrasound, and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) [13]. Terms used to describe breast parenchymal patterns, masses and

calcifications, related findings, and final assessment categories are all included in the lexicon [14].

There are seven evaluation categories for breast imaging studies:

- **BI-RADS Score- zero.**
require more imaging testing (ultrasound or additional mammogram views) and/or getting previous images for mammography that aren't available at the time of reading
- **BI-RADS 1 - negative.**
without any suspicious calcifications, masses, or architectural distortions, and symmetrical
- **BI-RADS 2- benign**
Malignancy probability of 0%
- **BI-RADS 3- probably benign**
<2% the probability of cancer
Short-term follow-up is suggested.
 - **BI-RADS 4: potentially malignant**
2–95% the probability of cancer
These can be further separated for ultrasound and mammography as follows:
 - BI-RADS 4A:** a low probability of cancer (2–9%)
 - BI-RADS 4B:** Moderate suspicion of malignancy (10–49%)
 - BI-RADS 4C:** 50–94% high suspicion of malignancy
 - **BI-RADS 5:** highly suggestive of cancer
>95% the probability of cancer.it is necessary to take the proper action.
 - **BI-RADS 6:** malignancy showed by biopsy

CONCLUSION

Mammography is a specialised form of breast radiography that creates images of the breast using x-rays. Screen film mammography (SFM) is a good evaluation, but it is not highly precise or entirely sensitive. Tomosynthesis improves the sensitivity and specificity of mammography, enhancing its clinical accuracy. Tomosynthesis-guided biopsy is a new and effective technique that patients tolerate well. The performance of radiologists and the patient experience will both be improved by the increased accuracy and general efficiency that DBT can offer. CEM is helpful for abnormal screenings, symptomatic patients, preoperative staging of breast cancer, evaluating response to neoadjuvant chemotherapy, screening women with dense breasts, and screening women at higher risk of breast cancer.

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